

AYTIS: THE POETIC FACE-OFF OF KARAKALPAK ORAL FOLKLORE

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Everyone knows perfectly well that language is a dynamic and developing system. The lexical stock of the Karakalpak language is constantly enriched. We do not notice that at the same time we forget the words of living folklore associated with natural phenomena, with raising children, with the perception of a work of art - be it Berdakh's poems or a fairy tale, a proverb, a ditty. As a result, the language does not develop, but becomes scarcer. To stop this process, it is necessary to strive not to lose the lexical riches of the native language, and probably turning to folklore is one of the most reliable ways to achieve this.

Folklore studies turn out to be important not so much for itself, but even for linguistics and literary criticism. The main source of oral traditions is the life of the people, traditions, and genesis. These texts reflect archetypes that contain a colossal amount of knowledge, are constantly reproduced and are of cultural value.

The most characteristic and original of Karakalpak oral folk art is “**Aytis**”.

Aytis is one of the leading genres of Karakalpak folklore and have evolved into one of the major genres since the 19th century. However, the genre of Aytis did not appear suddenly. Its various forms can be found in the literary traditions of the Greek, Roman, and other Western and Eastern countries.

The term “**Aytis**” is derived from the word "aytisiw" meaning "**to express through words.**" Therefore, it also signifies "to convey through beautiful words." One of the special forms of the art of beautiful speech has been present in Karakalpak literature since ancient times. It is accepted in the form of "Sòz jarisi" (Word contest) and "Dilwarlar"(Lovers) contests.

In the history of Karakalpak literature, there are three main types of this genre: 1) "Juwap aytıs" (Response aytıs), 2) "Sheshenlik aytıs" (Poetric aytıs), and 3) "Shayırlar aytısı" (Poets' aytıs).

"Shayırlar aytısı," which is the most developed form of this genre, holds a special place in literature from recent eras. It refers to the words, verses, or expressions created by poets, often highlighting their thoughts, feelings, or artistic interpretations. The "juwap aytıs" and "sheshenler aytısı" trace the historical origins of this genre.

The early "Juwap aytıs," having been a type of Karakalpak traditional poetic form, forms the foundation of the aytıs genre. The primary theme here is the testing of the intelligence of girls and boys. In times without theater, cinema, or other entertainment for young people, they engaged in friendly competitions, challenging one another. The conduct, decorum, and wit of these young men and women were all evaluated through their spoken words. The response was intense. Aytıs emerged in these contexts.

Since responses were conveyed through songs, this also formed a part of folk poetry. For example, when a boy offers a cup of tea to a girl, he says:

“Ju'zin'izde qalın'ız,
Tilin'izde palın'ız,
Bir kese shay usındıq,
Biyma'lel kelip alın'ız.”

“Take a sip from your cup,
Your words are like honey.
We offered you a cup of tea;
Please come and receive it.”

After the girl finishes drinking, she responds:

“Et esesin alar,
Balıq bahasın alar,
Shay bergen adam shalqaymay,
Qayıp kesesin alar.”

“The meat will be provided,

The price of the fish will be set.
Those who give tea shall not be idle.
They will take back their cup.”

In the *Response aytis*, there are not only responses regarding the cup of tea. The girls and boys also engage with one another, inviting each other to a word contest. For example, a girl might say:

“Bir kese shay berdik dep,
Awzına shıbın u'ymelep,
Bundayda jigit bolarma,
Shetinen gil gu'n'elek,”

“As you offered a cup of tea,
Standing still as a mouse,
Is there a boy who would behave like this,
When embarrassed, won't open their mouth?”

Whereas young man's response will be:

"So'z so'ylesek bıjıq boldıq.
So'ylemesek tırjıq boldıq.
Sha'rbaya qız ko'beygen son'.
En' son'ında injiq boldıq."

"If we speak, we become a talky.
If we don't, we become a dandy.
After the girl has increased in beauty,
In the end, we become quirky."

The essence of the response in the *aytis* is that it is based on words, and therefore, there are many intricate words used. However, in the pursuit of the response, all meanings come together.

“Ha'r eldin' o'z zan'ı boladı,
Tegis joldın' da shan'ı boladı,

Barlıg'in elestire bermen'.
Qız-jigittin' de pan'ı boladı.”

"Every nation has its own law,
And every road has its own dust.
Don't take everything in mind.
A girl and a boy also have their own dignity."

This is how it is expressed. Since the *aytis* is a form of folk poetry, it has both developed and underdeveloped forms. Some individuals who possess poetic talent elevate it to a deeper level of poetry. Therefore, the service they perform is somewhat different from that of the responses. In *response aytis*, the contributions of the authors are not very noticeable. The performers of these are people who have emerged from the community, “**jigit ag’ası**” (a young man called brother) and “**qız jen’gesi**” (a woman who teaches young girls). They may be known or unknown as masters of beautiful words.

On the other hand, the “**sheshen**” (bard or orator) and the “**shayır**” (poet) in the second group are known by their titles, which indicates their significance in the world of words. For example, in the *aytis* between Jiyrenshe (Among the Karakalpaks, there was a wise person named Jiyrenshe, who was a poet that conveyed the meaning of words) and the khan (title for ruler), the khan says:

“Qarasha degen qumırısqa.
Bir buyırıqtan qırılar,”

"The black folk is an ant that will be
crushed by a single command."

To which Jiyrenshe replies:

“Xalıq degen qanatın',
Qarashasız xan bolmas
Elin' bolar quwatın
Jalg'iz atta dan' bolmas”

"The people are your wings.

Without the folk, there is no khan.
Your strength will be your people,
A single horse cannot be a hero."

Thus, Jiyrenshe clearly illustrates that the happiness and prosperity of any khan are tied to their people. For this reason, the aytis genre has developed widely in Karakalpak folklore.

Its most remarkable examples can be seen in the Karakalpak oral literature, particularly in the aytis between Kunxoja and the Kazakh poet Sherniyaz, as well as in the aytis between A'jiniyaz and the Kazakh poetess Men'esh. Such literary traditions continue to exist in contemporary Karakalpak literature.

However, it should not be viewed solely as a traditional aspect of written literature. The reason is that the poets and sheshen who engage in aytis do so without pen and paper, relying on improvisation (reciting from memory). Therefore, this is considered one of the most developed forms of folklore tradition.

References:

1. Ma'mbetov.K., Jaqsi'mova.G., Nietova.R. (2013) "A'debiyat" pp 41-44 . 652s
2. Aymbetov K.(1965) "Karakalpak national storytellers". Tashkent
3. Pirnazarov.A (1992) «Jiyrenshe sheshen» . pp 201-204
4. Mamedov.N. (2007) Karakalpak literature T 200. pp 57-66
5. Baskakov. N.A. (1962) «The Turkic languages // Nations of Central Asia and Kazakhstan M., pp 34-39
6. Ордабаева, Д., & Сейтжанова, Л. (2023). Факторы, влияющие на способность к изучению языка. *Ренессанс в парадигме новаций образования и технологий в XXI веке*, 1(1), 412-414.
7. Сейтжанова, Л., & Ахметова, М. (2024). Qaraqalpaq hám inglís tillerinde kelbetliktiń dárejelerin salıstırıw. *Актуальные вопросы лингвистики и преподавания иностранных языков: достижения и инновации*, 1(1), 345-347.
8. Taxirovna, S. L. (2023). LINGUA-STYLISTIC ANALYSIS OF IDIOMATIC COMPOUNDS IN KARAKALPAK LITERATURE. *Новости образования: исследование в XXI веке*, 2(14), 331-333.
9. Luiza, S., & Kamila, K. (2024). STRUCTURAL COHESION AND INTEGRITY OF COMPOUNDS IN ENGLISH AND KARAKALPAK. *IJODKOR O'QITUVCHI*, 4(37), 158-160.